

Tsonga

Data source: eHRAF

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Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Bantu Religions, African Religions, Religious Group

The Tsonga are a group of Bantu-speaking people who have historically lived in what is now Mozambique and South Africa. This entry focuses on the Ronga sub-group around the time of 1895, and relies predominantly upon information recorded by the principal ethnographic authority (Junod, 1927ab). According to Junod (1927a), at the time this entry focuses on the Tsonga were composed of a number of clans, which formed six groups, including the Ronga. The primary social unit was the family and household. Several local households formed a village (led by a headman) and several villages formed a clan grouping (led by a chief). The central feature of Tsonga religion was ancestral spirits, known as shikwembu or ancestor-gods. Ancestor-gods were generally of two categories: those pertaining to the family and those pertaining to the country. The ancestor-gods of the chief's lineage were those pertaining to the country. A formal priesthood was not present, but certain individuals (eldest male in a household/lineage) were responsible for leading religious activity and conducting ceremonies. The main feature of such ceremonies involved propitiation of the ancestor-gods through sacrifice and offerings. Other magico-religious practitioners included those who used magic for evil (baloyi), those who used magic for the good of the community (wizards), medicine men, and divination specialists. Religious beliefs and practices permeated many aspects of society; consequently, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with society itself.

Date Range: 1880 CE - 1910 CE

Region: Tsonga lands, Ronga group ca. 1895

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Mozambique, Southern Africa, South Africa

Tsonga lands, Ronga group ca. 1895

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. (2004). Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: *Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: *Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ft06-002>

– Source 1 Description: Junod, H. A. (1927b). *The life of a South African tribe: vol. 2.* Macmillan and Co., Limited.

– Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ft06-001>

– Source 2 Description: Junod, H. A. (1927a). *The life of a South African tribe: vol. 1.* Macmillan and Co., Limited.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The principal ethnographic authority (Junod, 1927) was a Christian missionary living with the Tsonga (see Junod, 1927a:2).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating) was coded 0, indicating that no resolved rating was made (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating) was coded 0, indicating that no resolved rating was made (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because the Tsonga religious beliefs and practices permeate almost all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Consequently, membership is the default.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the Tsonga would actively proselytize and recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because the Tsonga religious beliefs and practices permeate almost all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Consequently, religion can be said to have political support.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of religious infrastructure.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: While the chief is not the official head of the religion, the chief must serve as the principal officiant at the luma ceremony (see Junod, 1927b:411).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates a conception of apostasy was present.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: A population figure is not listed for the Ronga group at the time this entry focuses on. "It is very difficult to ascertain the numbers of the Thongas. The census of the Transvaal taken on the 17th of April 1904 gives 82,325 as being the total Thonga population of that colony..." (Junod, 1927a:19).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Although there is not a formal priesthood among the Tsonga, certain individuals are responsible for leading religious activity. "The Thongas have no sacerdotal caste, but, as has already been pointed out, the right of officiating in religious ceremonies is strictly confined to the eldest brother. All offerings must be made through him. To supplant him is a great taboo, and would entail the malediction of the gods [the ancestor-gods], and even the death of the offender" (Junod, 1927b:411). Other magico-religious practitioners include those who use magic for evil (baloyi), those who use magic for the good of the community (wizards), medicine men, and divination specialists.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– I don't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "...the rites connected with the treatment of [spirit possession] are definitely magical, and those who have suffered from it often become recognized magicians, claiming to possess supernatural powers" (Junod, 1927b:479).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: "...the rites connected with the treatment of [spirit possession] are definitely magical, and those who have suffered from it often become recognized magicians, claiming to possess supernatural powers" (Junod, 1927b:479).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Column 6, Large or Impressive Structures, of Murdock and Wilson, 1972 (Note: equivalent to SCCS variable 66) "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "These [the Sacred Woods] are vast, almost impenetrable thickets, in which the ancient chiefs have been buried; they are called ntimu, (mu-mi) cemeteries. Every clan owns one or more of these burying places. The ntimu is reserved for the men of the royal family, those who have been the owners of the land" (Junod, 1927b:376).

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: "These [the Sacred Woods] are vast, almost impenetrable thickets, in which the ancient chiefs have been buried; they are called ntimu, (mu-mi) cemeteries. Every clan owns one or more of these burying places. The ntimu is reserved for the men of the royal family, those who have been the owners of the land" (Junod, 1927b:376).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "But although [Tsonga] locate the psychic faculties in the different organs, they certainly believe in an independent psychic principle, in a soul...They call it moya, spirit, and in the Ronga clans, hika, breath (the plurai mahika, in the expression 'ku ba ni mahika,' means to be out of breath)" (Junod, 1927b:362).

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: "But although [Tsonga] locate the psychic faculties in the different organs, they certainly believe in an independent psychic principle, in a soul...They call it moya, spirit, and in the Ronga

clans, hika, breath (the plurai mahika, in the expression 'ku ba ni mahika,' means to be out of breath)" (Junod, 1927b:362).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "But although [Tsonga] locate the psychic faculties in the different organs, they certainly believe in an independent psychic principle, in a soul...They call it moya, spirit, and in the Ronga clans, hika, breath (the plurai mahika, in the expression 'ku ba ni mahika,' means to be out of breath)" (Junod, 1927b:362).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Any man who has departed this earthly life, becomes a shikwembu, a god" (Junod, 1927b:372).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See the questions below for more details regarding the spatial location of the afterlife.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Some say that the departed go to a great village under the earth, a village where everything is white (or pure, 'ku basa'); there they till the fields, reap great harvests, and live in abundance, and they take of this abundance to give to their descendants on earth" (Junod, 1927b:375).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "Thus [a second idea is that] the life of the shikwembu seems to be the exact continuation of his earthly existence...A third idea, more or less intermediate between the other two, is that the gods reside in the sacred woods, and there lead their family life in human form, parents and children, even little children, who are carried on their mothers' shoulders" (Junod, 1927b).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "They lay the corpse down on its left side, the head on the pillow. The grave has been dug in such a way that its long axis is directed towards that cardinal point whence the ancestors came, so

that the deceased, having his head slightly bent backwards, is intended to look in that direction" (Junod, 1927a:138).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "They lay the corpse down on its left side, the head on the pillow. The grave has been dug in such a way that its long axis is directed towards that cardinal point whence the ancestors came, so that the deceased, having his head slightly bent backwards, is intended to look in that direction" (Junod, 1927a:138).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: See Junod, 1927a:138

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

Notes: See Junod, 1927a:138

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: See Junod, 1927a:138

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates cannibalism was practiced.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: "The bones of the dead are never disinterred. It is a taboo" (Junod, 1927a:167).

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates re-treatment of corpses was practiced.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of co-sacrifices in tomb/burial.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Clothing, mats, and earthen pots are described as grave goods (see Junod, 1927a:138).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: see Junod, 1927a:138

↳ Valuable items:

– No

Notes: Articles of value (such as knives, good baskets, hoes, etc.) are purified and distributed to the heirs of the deceased (see Junod, 1927a:141).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: After a death, "The men of the village then go out to dig the grave. They choose a place behind the hut of the deceased or somewhere further off in the little forest which generally surrounds the village; or in the ntimu, the sacred wood, if he were one of the guardians of the forest, one belonging to the elder branch of the family" (Junod, 1927a:136). For a full description of burial practices see Junod, 1927a, pp.136-144.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cenotaphs.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "These are vast, almost impenetrable thickets, in which the ancient chiefs have been buried; they are called ntimu, (mu-mi) cemeteries. Every clan owns one or more of these burying places. The ntimu is reserved for the men of the royal family, those who have been the owners of the land" (Junod, 1927b:376).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates family tomb-crypts were used.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates domestic burials took place.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Either behind household, in forest surrounding village, or sacred wood

Notes: After a death, "The men of the village then go out to dig the grave. They choose a place behind the hut of the deceased or somewhere further off in the little forest which generally surrounds the village; or in the ntimu, the sacred wood, if he were one of the guardians of the forest, one belonging to the elder branch of the family" (Junod, 1927a:136).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "Any man who has departed this earthly life, becomes a shikwembu, a god" (Junod, 1927b:372). "The two great categories of gods are those of the family, and those of the country, the latter being those of the reigning family. They do not differ as regards their nature. In national calamities those of the country are invoked, whilst, for purely family matters, those of the family are called upon" (Junod, 1927b:374).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– I don't know

Notes: The concept of Tilo (Heaven) is present, but does not appear to be viewed as a supreme high god. "Above the gods whom the common people know, worship, and call by name, there

exists a power which to the majority remains ill-defined and which they express by the word Heaven (Tilo). This word Tilo, which, in the ordinary language, is used to designate the blue sky (p. 304), contains a far deeper and more comprehensive meaning" (Junod, 1927b:428). "But Tilo is something more than a place. It is a power which acts and manifests itself in various ways. It is sometimes called Hosi, Lord. But this power is generally regarded as something entirely impersonal. Thongas appear to think that Heaven regulates and presides over certain great cosmic phenomena to which men must, willingly or unwillingly, submit, more especially those of a sudden and unexpected nature, by which I mean above all rain, storms, and, in human affairs, death, convulsions and the birth of twins" (Junod, 1927b:431).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Any man who has departed this earthly life, becomes a shikwembu, a god" (Junod, 1927b:372). "The two great categories of gods are those of the family, and those of the country, the latter being those of the reigning family. They do not differ as regards their nature. In national calamities those of the country are invoked, whilst, for purely family matters, those of the family are called upon" (Junod, 1927b:374).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "The apparitions of ancestor-gods in a human form in the sacred woods are not of frequent occurrence. The gods reveal themselves to their descendants by other and more common means; first, by their appearance in the form of animals, such as the Mantis (p. 335) or more often as little bluish-green snakes called shihundje (p. 340)" (Junod, 1927b:384).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Omniscience is also believed in: the gods know what their descendants do, though they may be separated from them, perhaps dwelling in distant lands. Omnipotence results from the fact that they control everything in the life of their descendants" (Junod, 1927b:425).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The domain in which they exercise their power is limited, being only that of their own family; they watch over their descendants, bless or punish them, but they are absolutely indifferent to other men, and do not trouble about their affairs more than they did when still alive on earth" (Junod, 1927b:425).

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– I don't know

Notes: According to the following example, ancestor-gods are capable of blessing their descendants. However, it is unclear if such blessings are viewed as rewards for specific actions/behaviors. "The domain in which they exercise their power is limited, being only that of their own family; they watch over their descendants, bless or punish them, but they are absolutely indifferent to other men, and do not trouble about their affairs more than they did when still alive on earth" (Junod, 1927b:425).

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: See Junod, 1927b:425

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "The spirits of the departed who wander about in the bush, not having been properly buried, try to attack innocent travellers" (Junod, 1927b:375).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: "The domain in which they exercise their power is limited, being only that of their own family; they watch over their descendants, bless or punish them, but they are absolutely indifferent to other men, and do not trouble about their affairs more than they did when still alive on earth" (Junod, 1927b:425).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "...the ancestor-gods communicate with the living in their dreams" (Junod, 1927b:384).

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: "...the ancestor-gods communicate with the living in their dreams" (Junod, 1927b:384).

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: "But the great means by which the will of the gods is revealed is the set of divinatory bones, which are cast on every occasion, and are called the 'Bula,' the Word" (Junod, 1927b:385).

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: A monarchy is not present among the Tsonga.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The two great categories of gods are those of the family, and those of the country, the latter being those of the reigning family. They do not differ as regards their nature. In national calamities those of the country are invoked, whilst, for purely family matters, those of the family are called upon "(Junod, 1927b:374). "Two other categories of gods, which I have sometimes heard mentioned, are the Gods of assagais (psikwembu psa matlhari) and the Gods of bitterness (psa shibiti)...The Gods of the Bush, Psikwembu psa Nhoba, are also especially dreaded" (ibid).

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– I don't know

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: "The two great categories of gods are those of the family, and those of the country, the latter being those of the reigning family. They do not differ as regards their nature. In national calamities those of the country are invoked, whilst, for purely family matters, those of the family are called upon "(Junod, 1927b:374). "Two other categories of gods, which I have sometimes heard mentioned, are the Gods of assagais (psikwembu psa matlhari) and the Gods of bitterness (psa shibiti)...The Gods of the Bush, Psikwembu psa Nhoba, are also especially dreaded" (ibid).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "The Thongas have no sacerdotal caste, but, as has already been pointed out, the right of officiating in religious ceremonies is strictly confined to the eldest brother. All offerings must be made through him. To supplant him is a great taboo, and would entail the malediction of the gods, and even

the death of the offender" (Junod, 1927b:411).

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thongas have no sacerdotal caste, but, as has already been pointed out, the right of officiating in religious ceremonies is strictly confined to the eldest brother. All offerings must be made through him. To supplant him is a great taboo, and would entail the malediction of the gods [the ancestor-gods], and even the death of the offender" (Junod, 1927b:411).

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Specific officiant of ceremonial activity

Notes: "The Thongas have no sacerdotal caste, but, as has already been pointed out, the right of officiating in religious ceremonies is strictly confined to the eldest brother. All offerings must be made through him. To supplant him is a great taboo, and would entail the malediction of the gods [the ancestor-gods], and even the death of the offender" (Junod, 1927b:411).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: "The only sin which seems to be deserving of punishment is to neglect them [the ancestor-gods]. There are, however, two other faults which they strongly condemn, and for which they may even kill their descendants: the first is any serious transgression against the law of hierarchy (as we saw, when dealing with the sacrifice of reconciliation); they punish especially the young man, even though he be the chief, who dares thus to encroach upon the right of the regular priest, which is a great taboo; secondly, they kill a man who loses all restraint in sexual relations...To other sins they are quite indifferent" (Junod:1927b:426).

↳ Adultery:

– I don't know

↳ Incest:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thongas have no sacerdotal caste, but, as has already been pointed out, the right of officiating in religious ceremonies is strictly confined to the eldest brother. All offerings must be made through him. To supplant him is a great taboo, and would entail the malediction of the gods [the ancestor-gods], and even the death of the offender" (Junod, 1927b:411).

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: "The only sin which seems to be deserving of punishment is to neglect them [the ancestor-gods]. There are, however, two other faults which they strongly condemn, and for which they may even kill their descendants: the first is any serious transgression against the law of hierarchy (as we saw, when dealing with the sacrifice of reconciliation); they punish especially the young man, even though he be the chief, who dares thus to encroach upon the right or the regular priest, which is a great taboo; secondly, they kill a man who loses all restraint in sexual relations...To other sins they are quite indifferent" (Junod:1927b:426).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "The only sin which seems to be deserving of punishment is to neglect them [the ancestor-gods]. There are, however, two other faults which they strongly condemn, and for which they may even kill their descendants: the first is any serious transgression against the law of hierarchy (as we saw, when dealing with the sacrifice of reconciliation); they punish especially the young man, even though he be the chief, who dares thus to encroach upon the right or the regular priest, which is a great taboo; secondly, they kill a man who loses all restraint in sexual relations...To other sins they are quite indifferent" (Junod:1927b:426).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See the questions below for more information regarding the cause of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Junod, 1927b:411

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thongas have no sacerdotal caste, but, as has already been pointed out, the right of officiating in religious ceremonies is strictly confined to the eldest brother. All offerings must be made through him. To supplant him is a great taboo, and would entail the malediction of the gods [the ancestor-gods], and even the death of the offender" (Junod, 1927b:411).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See the questions below for more information regarding the reason for supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– I don't know

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "The Thongas have no sacerdotal caste, but, as has already been pointed out, the right of officiating in religious ceremonies is strictly confined to the eldest brother. All offerings must be made through him. To supplant him is a great taboo, and would entail the malediction of the gods, and even the death of the offender" (Junod, 1927b:411).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: "It [the Tsonga religion] has no moral prescriptions except those which ensure the observance of the hierarchical order in the family. It neither promises reward nor threatens punishment after death" (Junod, 1927b:427).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: See the questions below for more information regarding supernatural punishment in this lifetime.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– I don't know

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "The Thongas have no sacerdotal caste, but, as has already been pointed out, the right of officiating in religious ceremonies is strictly confined to the eldest brother. All offerings must be made through him. To supplant him is a great taboo, and would entail the malediction of the gods [the ancestor-gods], and even the death of the offender" (Junod, 1927b:411).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: According to the following example, ancestor-gods are capable of blessing their descendants. However, it is unclear if such blessings are viewed as rewards for specific actions/behaviors. "The domain in which they exercise their power is limited, being only that of their own family; they watch over their descendants, bless or punish them, but they are absolutely indifferent to other men, and do not trouble about their affairs more than they did when still alive on earth" (Junod, 1927b:425).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: "Amongst the Thongas true adultery for a man, married or unmarried (bumbuye), consists in committing sin with a married woman" (Junod, 1927a:196).

Monogamy (males):

– I don't know

Monogamy (females):

– I don't know

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: "Amongst the Thongas true adultery for a man, married or unmarried (bumbuye), consists in committing sin with a married woman" (Junod, 1927a:196).

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: "Amongst the Thongas true adultery for a man, married or unmarried (bumbuye), consists in committing sin with a married woman" (Junod, 1927a:196).

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: For a complete description of taboos, see Junod, 1927b:574-577.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates physical risk-taking was required.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Although not explicitly required, propitiation of ancestral spirits (ancestor-gods) is highly emphasized and important (see Junod, 1927b:426). Propitiation of ancestor-gods is a family matter, and thus considered a small-scale ritual. See Junod, 1927b:388 for more information.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: One significant religious ceremony is “the great, the official Luma, amongst the Ronga clans, is that performed for the Kafir corn” (Junod, 1927a:396). During this ceremony, the chief and all sub-chiefs gather to propitiate ancestral spirits during the first fruits of the season.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– I don't know

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community, the Tsonga had two levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a larger chiefdom (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a formal education system.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food was stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food was stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Tuden and Marshall (1972) column 10, Police (note, equivalent to SCCS variable 90, Police) indicates that "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery."

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 149, Scale 1 (of Cultural Complexity)--Writing and Records, indicates that writing and records were not utilized (Murdock and Provost, 1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Tsonga relied primarily on extensive or shifting agriculture, with animal husbandry as a secondary form of subsistence. Hunting and fishing supplemented the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Tsonga relied primarily on extensive or shifting agriculture, with animal husbandry as a secondary form of subsistence. Hunting and fishing supplemented the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.